

Agro2Circular

D2.5 – Technologies for recycling of organic agrofood waste (public summary)

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Authors: Sofía Martínez López (CTNC)

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1 List of abbreviations

DES: Deep Eutectic Solvents

IL: Ionic Liquid

MAE: Microwave Assisted Extraction

NADES: Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents

SWE: Subcritical Water Extraction

UAE: Ultrasound Assisted Extraction

UF: Ultrafiltration

UPLC: Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography

WP: Work Package

2 Executive summary

Work package 2 (WP2) aims at implementing and optimizing technologies for the extraction and recycling of the agri-food waste generated in the Region of Murcia (Spain): citrus, apple, grape, cauliflower, broccoli and artichoke.

The specific objectives are:

- Establishing the conditioning of agrifood waste.
- Developing the optimal green hybrid extraction routes.
- Purifying and stabilizing extracts for their application in new formulations.
- Assessing the quality of extracts and their antioxidant and antimicrobial capacity.

Using different technological combinations, extraction processes have been optimised by means of extraction technologies, and purification and stabilisation technologies: green solvents + extraction assistance technologies + purification + stabilisation.

The routes applied can be defined as a first phase of treatment with green solvents, followed by a second phase of assistance with technologies such as ultrasound or microwaves. Unassisted green solvent extractions have also been evaluated. These routes also include purification and stabilisation steps.

Based on the results obtained, both from a technical and economic point of view, technological routes for the recycling of agri-food waste that are viable on an industrial scale have been selected:

- Fibre recovery: Enzymatic extraction combined with purification treatments by washing with oxidising agents and ultrafiltration has reported the highest extraction yields and purity.
- Phenolic compounds recovery: Microwave-assisted enzymatic extraction combined with purification treatments by adsorption/desorption with resins has reported the highest extraction yields and purity. Depending on further use, freeze-drying or microencapsulation of the actives has been selected as a delivery system.

3 CLASSIFICATION & CONDITIONING

Once the waste is received from the supplying companies, it is stored refrigerated/frozen depending on the time of processing for recycling.

It has not been necessary to carry out a prior waste classification process as waste is generated separately in the supplying companies which, as they work by production campaigns, generate waste from a single product.

In case there is no separate generation of agri-food waste, a first separation step should be carried out (this is because each waste has different compounds of interest to be recovered).

In general, different agri-food wastes have been subjected to mechanical or physical pre-treatments to reduce the size of the plant matrix and homogenise the sample. Particle size reduction is a factor that has long been taken into account as it facilitates mass transfer since the compounds of interest are more exposed to the solvent and therefore increases extraction speed and yields (Panzella et al., 2020). Thus, the plant material is shredded into 20 mm x 20 mm cubes (pre-treatment). Pre-treatments to reduce the granulometry of the waste have been carried out on all waste except for waste that initially has a small granulometry, as was the case with apple waste (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Particle size difference of apple (left) and broccoli (right) waste.

4 EXTRACTION METHODOLOGIES

4.1 GREEN SOLVENTS

In the field of extraction of compounds of interest, it is imperative to reduce the use of reagents and excipients in general and to eliminate the use of hazardous solvents in particular, or at least replace them with safer ones (Janicka et al., 2022).

This change must be achieved by ensuring sensitive, selective, accurate and robust methods, which allow high purity extracts to be obtained, require low treatment times and are cheap, sustainable and energy efficient (Janicka et al., 2022).

It has thus suggested an effort in the search for alternative solvents to conventional solvents, which can be detrimental to public health, safety and the environment due, in particular, to their volatility and toxicity. These new solvents can be considered green solvents (Yu et al., 2022).

Many of these solvents exhibit excellent results but require long processing times, so in many cases assistive or acceleration technologies are used to improve extraction efficiency and performance.

4.2 ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGIES

Assisted extraction techniques are an attractive alternative to conventional solvent extraction methods for extracting bioactive analytes from vegetable materials, as they allow significant improvements in extraction efficiency, provide high yields in short extraction times and reduce solvent requirements (Bachtler & Bart, 2020).

4.3 SELECTED METHODOLOGIES

The solvents initially selected were aqueous solvents, enzyme solutions, ionic liquids (IL), deep eutectic solvents (DES) and natural deep eutectic solvents (NADES).

Since the use of ionic liquids has been associated with some toxicity in the most current literature (and as evaluated using two different cell cultures), these solvents were discarded during the execution of WP2.

As an alternative, the use of subcritical water (SW) was proposed.

As auxiliary technologies, the study of ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) were proposed.

For this purpose, the extraction conditions using aqueous solvents, enzymatic extraction, extraction with subcritical water, extraction with DES, ultrasound-assisted extraction and microwave-assisted extraction were optimised, considering the different operational

parameters of each technology. The optimised operational parameters are shown in **Table 1**:

Table 1. Optimised operational parameters according to extraction technology.

Technology	Operational parameters
Aqueous extraction	Solid:liquid ratio (waste:solvent) Extraction temperature Treatment time
Enzymatic extraction	Enzyme used Enzyme dose
Ultrasound-assisted extraction	US amplitude
Microwave-assisted extraction	Solvent (NADES) MW power/temperature Treatment time
Subcritical water extraction	Extraction temperature Treatment time
Deep eutectic solvents extraction	DES used

After carrying out extraction trials for each technology with each of the selected agri-food waste, the following extraction routes have been selected as the most viable for semi-industrial scale-up:

- Enzymatic extraction
- Ultrasound-assisted extraction
- Microwave-assisted extraction

5 PURIFICATION & STABILISATION

The objective of this task is to establish and describe the methodologies for the purification and stabilisation of extracts (fibres, phenolics & carotenoids) obtained.

As a result of the different extractions carried out on the selected agri-food waste, a solid phase (particularly rich in fibre) and an aqueous phase (in which other compounds of interest such as phenolic compounds are found) have been obtained. Therefore, once the extraction process is finished, the liquid phase is separated from the solid phase by a 300 µm filtration process.

Once both extracts have been obtained, they have been subjected to purification and stabilisation treatments, in order to increase the concentration and purity of the target compounds, as well as to ensure their storage capacity and shelf life, respectively.

5.1 FIBRE PURIFICATION AND STABILISATION

For the purification of the fiber, treatments with oxidizing agents have been carried out by washing, which serves to oxidize any organic matter accompanying the fiber in order to make it as innocuous and clean as possible.

For this purpose, different reagents and reagent concentrations have been evaluated, looking for reagents that are compatible with the subsequent food use of the extracts.

Subsequently, the extract is washed twice with water to remove any remaining reagent from the extract. After washing, the extract is pressed to remove as much water as possible.

The pressed solid is dehydrated at 70 °C for 2 days to obtain a fibre powder.

Figure 2 shows the visual difference between a purified (B) and an unpurified (A) dehydrated fibre. As can be seen, the unpurified fibre has organic matter that contributes colour, but also odour and taste, which may therefore limit its application in new formulations by altering the organoleptic properties of the fortified food.

Figure 2. Fiber (A) unpurified; (B) purified

In order to purify the desired soluble fibres, the liquid obtained by centrifugation is sent to the ultrafiltration plant (UF). The retentate leaving the plant is finally concentrated in vacuum boules.

In both cases, the highest amounts of fibre extract are obtained with raw artichoke and lemon.

5.2 PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS PURIFICATION AND STABILISATION

The most commonly used techniques for liquid extract purification include ultrafiltration, diafiltration, adsorption/desorption methods, etc.

After evaluating these different purification techniques, the liquid extract, rich in phenolic compounds, has been purified using adsorption resins. The use of resins allows the selection and isolation of antioxidant compounds (flavonols, anthocyanins, tannins, phenolic acids, etc.) from the liquid extract by adsorption-desorption processes.

Different resins have been evaluated for this purpose. The first challenge was to find an adsorbent product that could specifically load a constant amount of the desired molecules without significant irreversible fouling due to adsorption. The second challenge was to elute the compounds of interest from the adsorbent and achieve the desired level of purity in the recovered product.

Figure 3. Purification with resins (A) at laboratory scale (B) equipment to be used for semi-industrial scale-up

The collected eluate is then concentrated by vacuum evaporation.

The highest concentrations of phenolic compounds have been detected in artichoke and grape residues.

To ensure the required stability of the extracted compounds of interest during the shelf life of food formulations, nutraceuticals and cosmetics, different stabilization and conservation methodologies have been tested.

Among the stabilization methodologies studied, freeze-drying and microencapsulation using different polymeric matrices have been selected.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Agri-food waste constitutes an important source of compounds of interest that can be recovered through waste recycling routes.

Artichoke wastes are established as one of the most promising due to their high fibre content and polyphenol-type antioxidant compounds.

Regarding the fibre content that can be recovered through the proposed extraction routes, broccoli and cauliflower residues are also established as interesting residues due to their high fibre content.

These extracts rich in fibre will be used in new food formulations, to obtain foods with a nutritional declaration of "rich in fibre" or "source of fibre".

Regarding the content of antioxidant compounds, such as polyphenols, the remains of lemon and grape have also been identified, together with the artichoke, as promising waste to be recycled.

These recovered antioxidant compounds constitute ingredients of high interest not only for new food formulations, but also for nutraceutical and cosmetic formulations.

In terms of the technologies proposed, enzymatic extraction is presented as the most versatile and efficient technology for the extraction of both fibre and polyphenolic compounds.

Microwave-assisted enzymatic extraction has shown a high extraction yield of phenolic compounds.

The combination of the extraction treatments just mentioned, with purification and stabilisation treatments, makes it possible to obtain extracts rich in antioxidant compounds and high purity fibre (between 70-80%).

Based on the results of this work package, the following recommendations are proposed to guide future actions:

- Promote the scale-up and industrial implementation of green extraction routes — especially enzymatic and water-based processes supported by assistive technologies— to valorise selected agri-food wastes like artichoke, lemon and broccoli.
- Explore the application of these technologies to other local agri-food wastes, with the aim of transferring and adapting the methodology to different regions and value chains.
- Ensure the safety, quality and functionality of the recovered ingredients, as demonstrated in the purification and characterisation stages, to support their use in food, nutraceutical and cosmetic products.

- Increase communication and transparency around the origin and benefits of upcycled ingredients, to build trust among consumers and facilitate acceptance by the food industry.

These steps will help turn waste into value, supporting circular bioeconomy strategies and encouraging the use of non-conventional raw materials in sustainable product innovation.

7 REFERENCES

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